

The Use of Directed Reading Thinking Activity (Drta) to Improve Students Reading Comprehension of the First Grade of Smk Pembangunan Kota Ternate

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Abstract

The Purpose of this research is to know the students reading comprehension can be improve by using directed reading thinking activity (DRTA) grade x of SMK Pembangunan Kota ternate .The research of implement classroom action research in two cycles. The subject in this research is the students of grade x of SMK Pembangunan Kota ternate school year 2018-2019 with amount students 20 people. This research is using in one class, each cycle consist of four phase that is: planning, action, observation and reflecting. Based on the result of classroom action research, in Cycle I there are 4 students who have met the KKM while 16 others have not yet reached KKM is due to, pay attention to the student when the teacher's explanation related implementation learning procedure using Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) method, activeness each student in identifying text in lucking, students activeness in making question and give the opinions in lucking. As well as the mistake that often student do incomprehension of the text as much 80%. Then in cycle II on the number of students who evaluated the overall reach KKM. This means that increasing students' comprehension by using Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) successfully.

Keywords: *directed reading thinking activity (DRTA)*, reading comprehension.

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1. Background

Reading is the active process read of understanding print and graphic texts and also Reading is a thinking process and reading is one of the skills of human in reading, as especially in parts of language. Reading can make every one each other know or understand something from the text and gat new information. In English department, reading is one of the skills that the students in understand something. And also Reading is one of the skills which must be taught to students as one of the teaching and learning activities in English class. Reading determines the successful of any subject matters. All depend on the competence of reading comprehension. But in reality, the students argue that reading is not interesting and they are still wrong to understand meaning of the text. They have difficulties in analysis, interpretation and make summary of the text. The students' need something produced some observation to make them more active and stimulate their interest in order to create an enjoyable atmosphere of English reading activity so that they can build up their reading comprehension particularly to their understanding the content of texts given.

Based on the result of observation on SMK PEMBANGUNAN KOTA TERNATE. The researcher finds some problems that make the researcher have to making research to change their view of English learning. Some problems are, the students' understanding in reading is beside that the students difficult to understand meaning of English text, and then the students difficult to determine main idea in reading text. Based on the problem above, the researcher want to improve the students' reading comprehension. The researcher need to apply one of a good method to make the students know more about English text and interesting strategy to make the students enjoy and more active in the class. It is DRTA strategy. The researcher using strategy directed reading thinking activity (DRTA) because, Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) is good strategy for all students, especially those with learning disabilities and or struggle need repetition within the same content in order to start to gain an understanding, and this strategy can faster making the students understand of English text.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Reading

Harrison and Salinger say that “reading is a complex activity and accomplished readers to operate a number of levels simultaneously. Harrison, Collin and Terry Salinger.(1998. p. 89).

Based on the definitions above, the writer concludes that reading is the active process of grasp meaning from the content of the writer's idea about the topic in a text.

Fluency begins to develop when student have frequent opportunities to read texts are easy for them. Multiple rereading of more difficult texts help broaden a readers fluency (pikulski,1998)

According to Alyousef (2005.144) says reading can be seen as an interactive process between a readers leads to automaticity or reading fluency.

According to Harmer (2007: 99) reading is useful for language acquisition. Provided that students more or less understand what they read, the more they read, the better they get at it.

Cline et.al (2006: 2), states that reading is decoding and understanding written texts.

Reading is a fluent process of readers combining information from a text and their own background knowledge to build meaning (Nunan, 2003).

2.2. Reading Comprehension

Reading comprehension has much deeper definition reading in general. However, reading comprehension has very close relation to reading and is almost cannot be separated when it comes to reading activity. As mikulecky (1990:2) says that reading can even be defined as practically synonymous with reading comprehension. Accordingly, most of readings goal is comprehend a text.

Westwood (2008:31) states that reading comprehension is an activity thinking process which a reader intentional constructs meaning form a deeper understanding of information presented in a text.

Comprehension can be defined broadly as the process of constructing a supportable understanding of a text (Neufeld, 2005)

According to Klingner, et al (2007:2) states that "Reading comprehension is the process of constructing meaning by coordinating a number of complex processes that include word reading, word and world knowledge, and fluency" Reading comprehension is primarily a matter of developing appropriate, efficient comprehension strategies.

2.3. Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA)

Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) is a technique that encourages students to make predictions while they are reading. After reading segments of a text, students stop, confirm or revise previous predictions, and make new predictions about what they will read next (Stauffer, 1969).

According to Clarck and Ganschow (1995:72) DRTA is a reading comprehension strategy that is used in each of the three stages of reading (pre-reading, during reading, and after reading).

According Russell Stauffer (1988:206) "Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) is a strategy that guides students in asking questions about a text, making predictions, and then reading to confirm or refute their predictions. The DRTA process encourages students to be active and thoughtful readers, enhancing their comprehension.

3. Method

Classroom Action Research is a method of finding out what works best in your own classroom so that you can improve student learning. We know a great deal about good teaching in general (e.g. McKeachie, 1999; Chickering and Gamson, 1987; Weimer, 1996), but every teaching situation is unique in terms of content,

Level , student skills and learning styles, teacher skills and teaching styles, and many other factors. Classroom action researches are a very effective way of improving your teaching. Assessing student understanding at mid-term helps you plan the most effective strategies for the rest of the semester. Comparing the student learning outcomes of different teaching strategies helps you discover which teaching techniques work best in a particular situation. Because you are researching the impact of your own teaching, you automatically take into account your own teaching strengths and weaknesses, the typical skill level of your students, etc.

The design of this research, the researcher used classroom action research to conduct this research. Classroom action research designed to solve practical problems in the process of teaching and learning, especially in teaching reading.

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1. Students' Achievement in Cycle I

In the cycle of the researcher found in class X, English lesson are not in demand by students' so that the material provided by researcher using Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) to improve students reading comprehension only a few students were able to solve the given task while another students is quiet with another blank stare chatting with his friend resulting increase students reading comprehension in the first cycle can seen in table 4.1 as follows

No	Nama students	Cycle I	Criteria of Success
1	Husnul hatimah	58	Not Complete
2	Agung kabir	66	Not Complete
3	Dahnil R.dapo	58	Not Complete
4	Farhurrahman	83	Complete
5	Dinul fajri	58	Not Complete
6	Nurafga talip	41	Not Complete
7	Asrul suhardi	58	Not Complete
8	Febriyanti djisman	75	Complete
9	Apriliya	83	Complete
10	Ulandari saban	50	Not Complete
11	Irfan ishak	50	Not Complete
12	Amita jawas	75	Complete
13	Dina burhan	50	Not Complete
14	Surtika juanda	50	Not Complete
15	Linda rusul M.torano	41	Not Complete
16	Foni Muhammad	50	Not Complete
17	linda hatari	58	Not Complete
18	Nurannisa F.hukum	33	Not Complete
19	Wiwin minggus	66	Not Complete
20	Sarmawan	58	Not Complete
	Total	1161	

Based on the table above can be seen that the students who have the highest score or reach KKM is 70, and the first, 83 obtained by two students, 75 obtained by two student, 58 obtained by six student, 66 obtained by two students and 50 is obtained by five students, 41 obtained by two students, 33 obtained by one students, From the result of research of obtained data above can know that criterion efficacy of this research still require to be improved by because still included in category not yet success.

4.2. Students' Achievement in cycle II

In the second cycle of this comprehension which is owned by the students is greatly increased using Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) this can be seen in the activity of students in following the teaching and learning process in the classroom. The resulting increase in the increase in comprehension that is owned by the students in the second cycle can be seen in table 4.2 as follows:

No	Nama students	Cycle II	Criteria of Success
1	Husnul hatimah	75	Complete
2	Agung kabir	83	Complete
3	Dahnil R.dapo	100	Complete
4	Farhurrahman	100	Complete
5	Dinul fajri	75	Complete
6	Nurafga talip	83	Complete
7	Asrul suhardi	66	Not Complete
8	Febriyanti djisman	100	Complete
9	Apriliya	66	Not Complete
10	Ulandari saban	58	Not Complete
11	Irfan ishak	58	Not Complete
12	Amita jawas	100	Complete
13	Dina burhan	58	Not Complete
14	Surtika juanda	66	Not Complete
15	Linda rusul M.torano	75	Complete
16	Foni Muhammad	91	Complete
17	linda hatari	83	Complete
18	Nurannisa F.hukum	75	Complete
19	Wiwin minggus	75	Complete
20	Sarmawan	58	Not Complete
	Total	1545	

Based on the table above can be seen that all students have had the highest score of reach KKM in writing recount text of 100 was obtained by four students, 83 obtained by three students, 75 obtained by five students, 66 obtained by three, 58 obtained by four student.

4.3. Discussion

Based on the results of classroom action research, the use Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) method can improve student reading comprehension. The first discussion in

answer the question of this problem formation it is teaching and learning in Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) method and the improvement of the students' ability in comprehension. This research use two cycles, from the data result above improve students reading comprehension at SMK Pembangunan before and after use Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA), there are different every cycles, after use DRTA method. Clarck and Ganschow (1995: 72) says that DRTA is a reading comprehension strategy that is used in each of the three stages of reading (Pre-reading, during reading, and post reading), And Majid (2008: 203-210) says "DRTA is able to produce readers who can" think, learn, and test. "From the results of the research above, it can be said that Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) method can improve students reading comprehension Of the First Grade of SMK Pembangunan Kota Ternate

4.3.1. Teaching and learning in Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) method.

Based on the results of classroom action research found , the use Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) in teaching and learning process can increase students reading comprehension. Increasing students' comprehension to stimulus and provide the text, involving student at each learning, especially in increasing students comprehension, so easy for them to understand of the text. So the use Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) method is appropriate when applied to the study of English in class at X SMK PEMBANGUNAN KOTA TERNATE and can be used by teacher in school as teaching method in the classroom.

4.3.2. The improvement of the student's ability in Comprehension

Based on the results of classroom action research found, the processes of learning on the students in the class X SMK have improved very well. It is found from the research result pre-cycle where in each cycle artifacts good improvement of each student's with a number of 20 students. Starting from pre-cycle there are 3 students have met the KKM and 17 others have not met the KKM , then in the first cycle of students who have met the KKM increase to 4 students' and 16 students others have not met the KKM while in the second cycle for all students has increased 100%. So this research has ended in the second cycle for all students have increased the ability to understand of the text.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of classroom action research that has been carried out in two cycles using the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) method in learning improve students reading comprehension Of The First Grade Of SMK Pembangunan Kota Ternate, it can be concluded that the Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA) method can improve students reading comprehension Of The First Grade Of SMK Pembangunan Kota Ternate

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